

Stability Constants of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Lanthanide(III) and Yttrium(III) with Complexone and Substituted Salicylic Acids

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Salicylic acid and substituted salicylic acids are potential antimicrobial agents¹. Binary complexes of salicylic acid and its substituted derivatives with lanthanide(III) and yttrium(III) metal ions have been reported². There are reports on the ternary metal complexing equilibria with some lanthanide(III) and yttrium(III) metal ions involving aminopolycarboxylic acid as one ligand and salicylic acid (SA) and other related compounds as the second ligand³. Ethyleneglycolbis(2-aminoethylether)-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetic acid (EGTA) is an important member of aminopolycarboxylic acid and finds many applications in medicine and biology. Recently, few ternary complexes have been reported using EGTA as ligand⁴. In view of biological importance of simple and mixed ligand complexes EGTA, SA and DNSA (3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid), a systematic study has been undertaken for the determination of stability constant and the results are reported here.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric titration curves corresponding to mineral acid, proton-ligand, metal-ligand and metal-ligand complexing systems are shown in Fig. 1. Curve-C representing the titration curve of 1 : 1 La(III)-H₂EGTA²⁻ system, diverges from the H₂EGTA²⁻ ligand titration curve-B in the initial stages of titration followed by a well-defined inflection at $a = 2$ ($a =$ moles of alkali per mole of ligand or metal) and $\text{pH} \approx 5.0$, indicating that La^{III} ion forms 1 : 1 chelate with H₂EGTA²⁻ in the lower pH range. This complex remains stable upto high pH values (≈ 10.0) and does not undergo hydrolysis upto this stage.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of La^{III}-EGTA-SA system: $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaNO₃), temp. = 25°.

Curve-E (Fig. 1) showing the pH-metric titration of 1 : 1 La(III)-SA binary complexing system, runs superimposed on the ligand titration curve-D upto $a = 1$ and $\text{pH} \approx 6.9$ indicating that there is no complex formation by La^{III} with salicylic acid upto this stage. The metal-ligand titration curve-E diverges from the ligand titration curve-D at $1 \leq a \leq 2$, $\text{pH} \approx 6.9$, suggesting complexation of the metal with the ligand SA which results in the liberation of extra protons. The equilibrium for this complexation reaction is :

La^{III}-SA binary titration curve further diverges towards volume axis and gives inflection at $a = 3$, indicating the liberation of extra one equivalent proton as a result of metal complex hydrolytic reaction in the range $2 \leq a \leq 3$, $pH \approx 7.0-8.2$,

The hydrolysis is further evidenced by the occurrence of opacity/turbidity during titration at $pH \approx 8.2$.

The proton dissociation constants of the ligands and the stability constants of binary and hydroxometal chelate species were calculated from the titration data using algebraic method⁵ and are presented in Table 1.

Curve-F (Fig. 1) represents the mixed ligand titration curve in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio and which runs superimposed on the theoretical composite curve-T upto $a = 3$ and $pH \approx 7.0$, indicating that secondary ligand does not participate in complexation reaction upto this stage. The formation of mixed ligand complex is suggested by the comparison of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand titration curve-F with the theoretical composite curve-T. In the range $3 \leq a \leq 4$, the experimental titration curve-F of mixed ligand system is displaced from the composite curve-T towards the right, suggesting the formation of mixed ligand complex. The chemical equilibria may be represented as

Table-1 (Contd.)

Metal-ligand system :	log K _{ML} ^M			
Ce ^{III} -H ₂ EGTA ²⁻	15.64	15.75	15.83	15.92
Pr ^{III} -H ₂ EGTA ²⁻	15.73	15.85	15.93	16.02
Nd ^{III} -H ₂ EGTA ²⁻	15.91	16.08	16.14	16.24
Sm ^{III} -H ₂ EGTA ²⁻	16.46	16.54	16.65	16.74
Gd ^{III} -H ₂ EGTA ²⁻	16.85	16.95	17.04	17.10
Y ^{III} -H ₂ EGTA ²⁻	16.92	17.01	17.09	17.18
La ^{III} -SSA	7.33	7.43	7.55	7.78
Ce ^{III} -SSA	7.53	7.66	7.74	7.96
Pr ^{III} -SA	7.75	7.86	7.95	8.17
Nd ^{III} -SA	8.15	8.26	8.35	8.56
Sm ^{III} -SA	8.34	8.48	8.65	8.82
Gd ^{III} -SA	8.54	8.62	8.73	8.95
Y ^{III} -SA	8.61	8.68	8.82	9.03
La ^{III} -SSA	5.73	5.78	5.85	5.99
Ce ^{III} -SSA	5.77	5.84	5.98	6.18
Pr ^{III} -SSA	5.85	5.92	6.04	6.24
Nd ^{III} -SSA	6.36	6.43	6.53	6.73
Sm ^{III} -SSA	6.58	6.65	6.75	6.94
Gd ^{III} -SSA	7.26	7.37	7.40	7.57
Y ^{III} -SSA	7.33	7.41	7.48	7.63
La ^{III} -DNSA	4.75	4.83	4.95	5.18
Ce ^{III} -DNSA	4.88	4.98	5.13	5.36
Pr ^{III} -DNSA	5.05	5.13	5.33	5.53
Nd ^{III} -DNSA	5.39	5.44	5.59	5.78
Sm ^{III} -DNSA	5.59	5.69	5.85	6.04
Gd ^{III} -DNSA	5.75	5.83	6.01	6.22
Y ^{III} -DNSA	5.82	5.89	6.10	6.31
Hydroxometal ligand systems :	-log K _{M(OH)L} ^{ML}			
La ^{III} (OH)-SA	8.01	8.04	8.09	8.20
Ce ^{III} (OH)-SA	7.98	8.00	8.02	8.12
Pr ^{III} (OH)-SA	7.90	7.94	7.99	8.09
Nd ^{III} (OH)-SA	7.87	7.91	7.94	8.06
Sm ^{III} (OH)-SA	7.82	7.86	7.91	8.02
Gd ^{III} (OH)-SA	7.74	7.80	7.85	7.90
Y ^{III} (OH)-SA	7.69	7.72	7.78	8.81
La ^{III} (OH)-SSA	7.85	7.89	7.94	8.07
Ce ^{III} (OH)-SSA	7.79	7.84	7.90	8.02
Pr ^{III} (OH)-SSA	7.74	7.80	8.85	9.00
Nd ^{III} (OH)-SSA	7.71	7.76	7.81	7.88
Sm ^{III} (OH)-SSA	7.67	7.72	7.78	7.83
Gd ^{III} (OH)-SSA	7.63	7.68	7.73	7.79
Y ^{III} (OH)-SSA	7.59	7.63	7.69	7.73
La ^{III} (OH)-DNSA	7.56	7.60	7.65	7.79
Ce ^{III} (OH)-DNSA	7.49	7.54	7.59	7.73
Pr ^{III} (OH)-DNSA	7.44	7.48	7.53	7.68
Nd ^{III} (OH)-DNSA	7.37	7.41	7.46	7.62
Sm ^{III} (OH)-DNSA	7.28	7.34	7.39	7.54
Gd ^{III} (OH)-DNSA	7.20	7.26	7.31	7.45
Y ^{III} (OH)-DNSA	7.16	6.22	7.30	7.40

TABLE I—THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS OF PROTON-LIGAND, METAL-LIGAND AND HYDROXOMETAL-LIGAND SYSTEMS

Proton-ligand system :	$\mu = 0.15 M$	$\mu = 0.10 M$	$\mu = 0.05 M$	$\mu \rightarrow 0$
	pK ₁ / (pK ₂)			
H ₂ EGTA ²⁻	8.73 (10.37)	8.86 (10.55)	9.05 (10.62)	9.18 (10.75)
A	2.97 (12.37)	3.11 (12.61)	3.17 (12.83)	3.43 (12.98)
SA	2.92 (10.68)	3.03 (10.78)	3.10 (10.91)	3.33 (11.07)
SA	1.51 (7.37)	1.66 (7.52)	1.88 (7.75)	2.12 (7.89)
tal-ligand em :	log K _{MA} ^M			
¹ -H ₂ EGTA ²⁻	15.25	15.37	15.47	15.55

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES, $\Delta \log K$ AND (%) R.S.

Ternary system	$\mu = 0.15 M$ $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\mu = 0.10 M$ $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\mu = 0.05 M$ $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\mu \rightarrow 0$ $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	(%) R.S.
La ^{III} -EGTA-SA	5.18	5.37	5.54	5.72	-2.06	-26.48
Ce ^{III} -EGTA-SA	5.32	5.45	5.62	5.77	-2.19	-27.51
Pr ^{III} -EGTA-SA	5.51	5.65	5.69	5.81	-2.36	-28.89
Nd ^{III} -EGTA-SA	5.57	5.72	5.78	5.89	-2.67	-31.19
Sm ^{III} -EGTA-SA	5.65	5.83	5.94	5.09	-2.73	-31.89
Gd ^{III} -EGTA-SA	5.74	5.86	5.95	6.13	-2.85	-31.74
Y ^{III} -EGTA-SA	6.81	6.91	6.03	6.21	-2.82	-31.23
La ^{III} -EGTA-SSA	4.86	5.05	5.15	5.26	-0.73	-12.19
Ce ^{III} -EGTA-SSA	4.99	5.14	5.22	5.36	-0.82	-13.27
Pr ^{III} -EGTA-SSA	5.07	5.17	5.26	5.42	-0.82	-13.14
Nd ^{III} -EGTA-SSA	5.16	5.26	5.34	5.48	-1.25	-18.57
Sm ^{III} -EGTA-SSA	5.27	5.37	5.44	5.60	-1.34	-19.30
Gd ^{III} -EGTA-SSA	5.33	5.44	5.54	5.69	-1.88	-24.83
Y ^{III} -EGTA-SSA	5.41	5.52	5.65	5.74	-1.89	-24.77
La ^{III} -EGTA-DNSA	4.43	4.55	4.76	4.97	-0.79	-15.25
Ce ^{III} -EGTA-DNSA	4.57	4.67	4.83	5.04	-0.61	-17.54
Pr ^{III} -EGTA-DNSA	4.65	4.76	4.84	5.08	-0.49	-08.86
Nd ^{III} -EGTA-DNSA	4.78	4.84	5.02	5.18	-0.70	-12.11
Sm ^{III} -EGTA-DNSA	4.87	4.97	5.11	5.42	-0.60	-09.93
Gd ^{III} -EGTA-DNSA	5.01	5.12	5.17	5.49	-0.73	-11.73
Y ^{III} -EGTA-DNSA	5.10	5.24	5.29	5.57	-0.74	-11.72

The formation of mixed ligand complex is further supported by non-appearance of opacity/turbidity throughout the mixed ligand titration, whereas turbidity appeared in 1 : 1 binary systems of SA, SSA and DNSA.

On the mixed ligand titration curve in the range $0 \leq a \leq 4$ concentrations of ligand H_2A^{2-} (C_A), ligand H_2L (C_L) and metal M (C_M) are given by the following expressions : $C_A = [H_2A] + [HA] + [A] + [MA] + [MAL]$; $C_L = [H_2L] + [HL] + [L] + [MAL] + [ML]$; $C_M = [M] + [MA] + [ML] + [MAL]$. The above mass and charge balance relations are used to determine the stability constant of ternary complexes. These values are presented in Table 2 together with percentage of relative stabilisation, (%) R.S. = $(\Delta \log K / \log K_{MAL}^M) \times 100$, where $\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{MAL}^M$. Negative values of

(%) R.S. indicate that the secondary ligand (L) binds better to aquometal ion than the binary $[M.EGTA]^-$ complex. It can be explained on the basis of the electrostatic repulsion between $[M.EGTA]^-$ and L^- ligand, coupled with the availability of lesser number of coordination sites for coordination on $[M.EGTA]^-$ binary complex compared to aquated metal ion.

The percentage distribution of metal ion among various complex species as a function of pH has been plotted. Stability orders of the binary and ternary complexes are found to be in accordance with the increasing ionic potential of metal(III) ions, i.e. $La < Ce < Pr < Nd < Sm < Gd < Y$, and the stability sequence with respect to secondary ligand follows the basicity order of the ligands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The lanthanide(III) and yttrium(III) solutions were prepared by dissolving their nitrates and standardised.

An Elico LI-120 pH-meter fitted with glass and calomel electrodes was used and standardised using buffer solutions of pH 4.00 and 9.20. Six titration mixtures of the following compositions were pre-

pared : (i) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO_3 ; (ii) (i) + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand A; (iii) (ii) + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion; (iv) (i) + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand L; (v) (iv) + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion; (vi) (ii) + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ligand L + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion, where A = disodium salt of ethyleneglycolbis(2-aminoethyl ether)- N,N,N',N' -tetraacetic acid (H_2EGTA^{2-}), L = salicylic acid, 5-sulphosalicylic acid and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid, and metal(III) ions are La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd and Y. Total volume of each titration mixture was kept at 50 ml. Requisite volume of 1 M sodium nitrate solution was added to maintain the desired ionic strengths, viz. 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 M.

References

1. Y. ANJANEYULU, R. Y. SWAMY and R. P. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **63**, 346; D. R. H. GOURLEY in "Medical Chemistry", ed. E. BURLE, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1960; A. ALBERT, "Selective Toxicity", Chapman and Hall, London, 1979.
2. S. B. PIRKES and A. V. LAPITSKAYA *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1976, **20**, 14; A. CASSOL and P. DIPERNARDO, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1972, **102**, 1118; I. M. BATYAEV and N. L. PZANKOVA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1973, **18**, 981; S. N. DUBEY and B. C. BHUVAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 442; G. R. CHOPPIN and N. C. LIUQING, *Lanthanide Actinide Res.*, 1986, **5-6**, 285; T. A. BARONOVA, S. B. PIRKES, N. A. KOSTROMINA, L. B. NOVIKOVA and I. A. TERTIAKOVA, *Ukr. Khim. Zh.*, 1989, **55**, 119; T. A. BORANOVA, S. B. PIRKES, A. A. BUGAEVSKIS, YU. V. KHOLIN and N. A. KOSTROMINA, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1991, **23**, 543; S. B. PIRKES and A. V. LAPITSKOVA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1975, **20**, 1415.
3. A. M. PIRKES and K. N. MUNSHI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 636; S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA, *J. Inst. Chem.*, 1985, **57**, 79; A. K. PANDEY, M. CHANDRA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 924; *Rev. Chem. Miner.*, 1980, **17**, 214; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 32, 227; S. VERMA and M. C. SAXENA, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1990, **39**, 75.
4. R. AHUJA and K. DWIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 643; R. AHUJA and K. DWIVEDI, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1993, **5**, 74.
5. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 392.
6. R. NAYAN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 383.